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Contemporary Trends In Agricultural Education Programme In State- Owned Colleges Of Education, Delta State, Nigeria

Minna-Eyovwunu, D., & Emadu, Eden Igbunuoghene

College of Education Warri, Delta State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The research was carried out to determine the contemporary issues in the NCE agricultural education programme in the two state-owned Colleges of Education, Delta State. The population of the study comprises of all the lecturers and the technical staff in the State- owned Colleges of Education, Delta State; specifically, the College of Education, Warri and College of Education, Mosogar. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select these two Colleges. The population of the study is the same as sample size as it is small and manageable. A descriptive survey research design was used to carry out the study; data collection instruments included a self-structured questionnaire and personal interviews. A 36-item self-structured questionnaire titled: *Assessment of Contemporary Trends in Agricultural Education Programme in State-owned Colleges of Education in Delta State* (AOCTAEPSOCOEDSQ) was used for data collection. The instrument was divided into two sections: Section (A) and (B) which deals with the availability and adequacy of resources and facilities; structured in a categorical variables of two groups to seek response from the respondents on the availability and adequacy of resources/facilities; and on a 4-Likert scale of evaluation, respectively, to solicit response from the respondents on the current issues in NCE agricultural education programme. The data generated were analyzed using descriptive statistics: Mean, standard error of means, frequency distribution count, and simple percentages; while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and non-parametric independent sample T-test were used to test the null hypothesis. The findings indicated a significant decline in the level of admissions to the two Colleges of Education and also identified, among other issues, inadequate funding, low student enrollment, an unfavorable environment, poor provision of infrastructural facilities, insufficient or non-availability of equipment, and a shortage of professional and technically qualified staff, declining quality of research and teaching etc, these factors represent the current trends in the NCE agricultural education Programme in the state-owned Colleges of Education investigated.

Keywords: Contemporary trends, agricultural education programme, Colleges of education

INTRODUCTION

Technical and vocational education and training (TVET) is a comprehensive term referring to those aspect of educational process involving in addition to general education; the study of related technologies and related sciences and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life (Nigeria Educational Research and Development Council [NERDC] 2013). According to United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO] (2015) TVET is a comprehensive term compressing education, training and skills development relating to a wide range of occupational fields, production, services and livelihoods. It aims, amongst other things is to provide technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agricultural, commercial and economic development, and to impact necessary skills for economic self-reliance.

Agricultural education, as defined by Osinem (2008) is the process of impacting knowledge, attitudes, and skills to learners at any level of education in agriculture. While, Egbule (2002) defined agricultural education as the type of education employed in training learners in the process of agricultural productivity as well as techniques for teaching agriculture i.e. it involves the acquisition of knowledge, skills and attitudes in agriculture.

The philosophy of Nigeria certificate in Education [NCE], agricultural education programme is tied with the national philosophy on agriculture for self-reliance based on the provision of teachers endowed with a balanced approach between principles and practice of Agriculture for academic and vocational ends. The objectives of the programme shall be to prepare graduates with the right attitude to, and knowledge/professional competence in vocational agriculture; to produce teachers who will be capable of motivating students to acquire interest in and aptitude for agriculture; to develop in the student-teacher the appropriate communicative skills for effective transmission of agricultural information and skills to the students in the context of their environment; to equip the student-teacher with adequate knowledge and ability to establish and manage a model school farm effectively; to provide a sound background to enhance further academic and professional progression of the student-teacher (National Commission for Colleges of Education [NCCE] 2012).

The Nigeria National Policy of Education [NPE] 2004) stated the aims of vocational technical education as follows:

- a) The provision of trained manpower in applied science, technology and commerce particularly at sub-professional grades;
- b) The provision of necessary technical knowledge for vocational skills necessary for agriculture, industry, commercial and economic development;
- c) The provision of people who can apply scientific knowledge to the improvement of and solution of environmental problems for the convenience of man;
- d) The giving of training and impacting the necessary skill's leading to the production of craftsmen, technicians and other skilled personnel who will be enterprising and self-reliant; and
- e) The enabling of young men and women to have an intelligent understanding of the increasing complexity of technology.

Agricultural education programme in tertiary institutions is therefore geared towards producing graduates with skills, competencies, knowledge and attitudes in agriculture for self-reliance and livelihood; and contribute considerably to the economic growth of the nation. Agricultural education programme environment is the general condition of human and material resources in which teaching and learning takes place. A good agricultural education programme environment provides technically and pedagogically qualified staff, modern recommended facilities and equipment for effective and meaningful teaching and learning. UNESCO (2012) opined that effective teaching and learning of curriculum requires efficient systems that provides learning environment with adequate access to teaching-learning resources. Learning Liff-off (2016) asserted that learning environment plays a significant role in student success, and that institutions of learning can potentially lift student's achievement by improving their learning environment.

Agricultural education in Nigerian tertiary institutions in contemporary times are being plagued with low enrollment of students; lack of funding; inadequate availability of modern and functional tools and equipments; inadequate infrastructural facilities and resources for effective teaching and learning etc.

Agricultural education is one of the vocational programmes in the tertiary institutions (Colleges of Education, Polytechnics and Universities) that equip learners with knowledge and skills required in productive agriculture. It is the training of head and hands of learners; i.e. the use of scientific knowledge in the teaching and learning of food production through acquisition of knowledge of crop production, livestock management, soil and water conservation and other associated products for industrial and human development (Hayes & Stewart, 2016). It is a type of vocation that emphasizes preparation and participation in an occupation for social value (Whadahan, 2015). Opposing to general education, agricultural education is skill oriented in training of enrollee for self-reliance and job creation (Okoye & Udodo, 2015). Agricultural education and training inculcate in students passion to engage in practical agricultural activities in crop production, livestock farming, processing,

marketing and storage of farm products in order to help achieve food security and actualize the objective of sustainable national development (Balala, 2019).

Low enrollment of students in vocational agricultural education (VAE):

Freddie (2004) noted that the decline in the number of students entering the field of agriculture has been on the rise over the years. Dai Kosi et al. (2008) reported that there are thousands of young university graduates roaming the streets in search of seemingly unavailable jobs. Jarson et al. (2014) asserted that recent graduates are finding it increasingly difficult to secure jobs, and those who do find jobs are often confined to low wage position. Where there is dearth in job availability post – graduate students will find it difficult to enroll in any of such programme. Okiror and Otubong (2015) opined that Agricultural courses are perceived as a course reserved for the less intelligent and less privilege, and students who study agriculture at the university often do so by chance, assignment from the selection body rather than by choice. The image and perception of students about agricultural education needs positive change (Baliyan & Nenty, 2015). Therefore, there is an urgent need to encourage students to enroll into agricultural education programme by creating a conducive and efficient environment for agricultural education programme for quality teaching and learning.

Agricultural education programme environment:

The environment is a potent element for quality education. Environment comprises facilities, resources (material/human) and avenues used in teaching and learning. Agricultural education programme environment therefore, refers to the general conditions (of human & material resources; and avenues) under which agricultural education is imparted / learned. Tan and So (2018) opined that interaction with the environment presents authentic learning opportunities that learners can tap from. Ekundayo (2012) stated that there is a significant relationship between school facilities and students achievement in the psychomotor and affective domains. While Usaini et al. (2015) opined that students from schools with adequate facilities, good teachers and favourable environment perform better than those from schools with fewer facilities, unqualified teachers and the less enabling environment. A good agricultural education programme environment ought to be equipped with technically and pedagogically qualified staff and have modern recommended facilities and equipment for effective teaching and learning.

Learning environment plays a significant role in student's success, and that institution of learning can potentially lift student's achievement by improving their learning environment (Learning Lift-off, 2016). UNESCO (2012) averred that effective teaching and learning of curriculum requires efficient systems that provide learning environment with adequate access to teaching-learning resources.

Inadequate personnel in agricultural education:

Boone and Boone (2007) asserted that if the agricultural education profession is going to grow and prosper in the 21st century, the system needs to provide quality and qualified teachers. Bamiro (2012) stated that achievement of good quality education will be great if the needs of lecturers are met. Achievement of good quality education in tertiary institutions needs personnel's of good qualities, and knowledgeable in the subject areas. Without adequate numbers of quality inspiring personnel, well prepared to meet their responsibilities in class and research works, educated personnel will be difficult to acquired (John & Agba, 2010). Ajayi (2007) stated that good personnel are needed for good quality education which in turn is essential for social change, societal transformation and national growth. The importance of agricultural personnel cannot be over emphasized.

Poor provision of infrastructural facilities:

The national university commission's need assessment survey which was reported by Emmanuel (2008) indicated that about 30% of Nigeria student's population has adequate access to workshops, laboratories, classrooms, lecture halls and libraries. It also reports that libraries are deficient in terms of current books, journals and electronics support facilities. Odetunde (2004) reported that students of tertiary institutions are studying in poorly ventilated, illuminated and dilapidated classrooms buildings which are environmentally demoralizing. Some lecturers share small offices and hope for future when they will have proper accommodation, but the future is never realized in a lot of institutions instead the situation is getting worst. Oyesola (2016) also reported that infrastructural facilities like electricity, water supply and roads are lacking in Nigeria, consequently the growth of the institutions are adversely affected.

Poor funding of VAE in tertiary institutions:

Poor funding is the most serious issue that has threatened the achievement of good quality education in Nigeria. Canice et al. (2007) maintained that a major constraint to attaining academic excellence in tertiary institutions is financial challenges which make many institutions of higher learning in Nigeria unable to build lecture halls and student's hostels, equip laboratories and workshops, and pay staff salaries, research grants and allowances.

Other issues of concern in VAE in Nigeria:

Minna-Eyovwunu et al. (2020) averred that VTE are constraints with issues such as inadequate funding, lack of interest on the part of the students, poor public perception and apathy to VTE, lack of training facilities/technical personnel, high cost of purchasing VTE equipment, shortage of qualified vocational technical teachers, curriculum defect, poor remuneration of teachers/technical personnel, lack of indigenous textbooks, deregulations of Nigeria economy, poor financing and implementation of VTE programmes, Nigeria value system, academically weak entrants, and corruption amongst others. Egbule (2002) reported that agricultural education programme is constraints with such problems as inadequate finance, insufficient or non-availability of equipment, and shortage of professional and technically qualified staff. While Egbita (2007) decries that most TVET institutions lack equipments and good learning environment to function properly for trainees to gain practical experience in their chosen vocations. Kyarize (2015) wonders why teachers still train students solely in the confinement of their schools, when only very few schools have well-equipped workshops that stimulate real works environment. This leaves learners limited opportunities to acquire the necessary skills and competences to function in the world of work.

Ekong and Eicher (2006) stated issues of concern to includes inadequate funding, poor infrastructures, the declining quality of research and teaching, expertise needs to guide policy and relevant research for the development of the country. Aina (2009) averted that the curriculum in schools is outdated, not functional to produce graduates with employable skills. The educational plan of a subject with down to earth content is commonly composed into a normal of 67% for the hypothetical classes and 33% for workshop.

The literature reviewed indicated the various contemporary issues in tertiary institutions to include the followings: inadequate availabilities of resources/facilities, low enrollment into the programme, inadequate qualified professionals and technical staff, poor funding, poor infrastructures, and declining quality research and teaching, amongst others in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria; but there is a dearth of information's on contemporary trends in agricultural education in Colleges of Education in Delta State. Therefore the research tends to bridge the gap.

Problems Statement/Justification

Agricultural education is one of the vocational programmes in Colleges of Education that equip students with skills, and competencies required in productive agriculture for self-reliance, job creation, and to contribute significantly to the economic growth of the nation. Agricultural education programme in contemporary time is being faced with a lot of challenges, thereby making it difficult to achieve the national philosophy on agriculture for self-reliance; and the laudable objectives of the programme; and that of the national policy of education for sustainability, job creation, productivity and economic growth.

Egbule (2002) opined that agricultural education programme is plagued with such challenges as inadequate finance, insufficient or none availability of equipment, and shortage of professionally and technically qualified staff. Egbita (2007) posits that most TVET institutions lack equipment and good learning environment to function properly for learners to gain practical experience in their chosen vocations. Consequently, these issues have lead to high rate of unemployment for TVET graduates; and instead of being self-reliant and productive, and contributing to the economy, they are roaming about the street looking for white collar jobs that are not available. Therefore, this research stands to investigate the contemporary trends in the NCE agricultural education programme in the state owned Colleges of Education in Delta State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the research was to investigate the current trends in vocational agricultural education programme in state-owned Colleges of Education, Delta State. Specifically, is to determine the:

- I. Availability and adequacy of infrastructural facilities and resources for teaching and learning in the NCE agricultural education programme.
- II. Level of enrollment in the NCE agricultural education programme.
- III. Contemporary challenges affecting efficient teaching and learning in the NCE agricultural education programme.

Research Questions

- I. What are the level of availability and adequacy of facilities and resources for teaching and learning in the NCE agricultural education programme?
- II. What is the level of enrollment in the NCE agricultural education programme?
- III. What are the contemporary challenges affecting efficient teaching and learning in the NCE agricultural education programme?

Hypothesis

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the mean level of enrollment in the NCE agricultural education programme between the State-owned Colleges of Education

Ho₂: there is no significant difference in the mean level of the contemporary issues affecting the NCE agricultural education programme between the State- owned Colleges of Education

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey research design was employed to carry out this study. The population of the study comprises of all the lecturers and the technical staff in the state-owned Colleges of Education in Delta State (College of Education, Warri; and College of Education, Mosogar). A purposive sampling technique was employed to select the two State owned Colleges. The population for the study is the same as sample size as it is small and manageable. A 36-item self-structured questionnaire titled: *Assessment of Contemporary Trends in Agricultural Education Programme in the State-owned Colleges of Education in Delta State* (AOCTAEPSOCOEDSQ) was used for data collection. The instrument was divided into two sections: Section (A) and (B) which deals with the availability and adequacy of resources and facilities; structured in a categorical variables of two groups: 1- (available) and 2- (not available) to seek response from the respondents on the availability and adequacy of resources/facilities; and on a 4-Likert scale of evaluation: Agree (A), strongly agree (SA), disagree (D) & strongly disagree (SD); with corresponding values of 1, 2, 3, and 4 respectively; to solicit response from the respondents on the current issues in NCE agricultural education programme. The standard for determining the acceptability of a factor was established at an average mean point of ≤ 2.50 , with any factor below this threshold being rejected; conversely, a decision point of 50% and above was designated as acceptable regarding the availability and adequacy of the resources and facilities being examined.

A comparative evaluation of twelve-year period of admission data between 2013/2014 – 2024/2025 academic session of the NCE agricultural education programme in State - owned Colleges of Education was carried out. The admission data for the period in question were collected from the respective admission officers of the Colleges of Education in the area of study.

The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by experts from the Colleges of Education. The test-re-test reliability assessment was used to determine the internal consistency of instrument. The reliability of the instrument was carried out with the Cronbach's Alpha model, which gave a coefficient value of 0.82 signifying greater reliability.

The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics: frequency distribution count, and simple percentages; while Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and non-parametric independent sample T-test were used to test the null hypothesis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table I. Frequency distribution on availability and adequacy of resources and facilities

Resources / facilities	Available	Not Available
Classroom (space & Equipment)	100% (27)	-
Laboratory for crops and soil	59.3% (16)	40.7% (11)
Livestock Unit	59.3% (16)	40.7% (11)
Fish pond	59.3% (16)	40.7% (11)
Individual student plot	88.9% (24)	11.1% (3)
Experimental plot	63% (17)	37% (10)
Crop farm	100% (27)	-
Facilities for bee keeping, snail or cane rat farming	-	100% (27)
Mechanical/ tools workshop	18.5%(5)	81.5% (22)

Source: Field survey, 2025

*Values in parenthesis () are frequency values

Table 1. Indicated that classroom (space & equipment), laboratory for crops and soil, livestock unit, fish pond, individual student plot, crop farm; with percent and frequency value of 100% (27), 59.3% (16), 59.3% (16), 59.3% (16), 88.9% (24), 63% (17) & 100% (27), respectively, with percent values of 50% and above indicated their availability in the study area. Classroom (space & Equipment) (100% (27), individual student plot 88.9% (24) and crop farm 100% (27), are among the few resources/facilities that are adequately available. In contrast, facilities for bee keeping, snail or cane rat with percent and frequency value of 0% and 18.5% (5) respectively, revealed their none availability in the study area. The results of the present study are in agreement with the findings of (Emmanuel, 2008; Odetunde, 2004; & Oyesola, 2016) as stated earlier on.

Table 2. Frequency distribution of responses on the availability and adequacy of staff office, books in the library and other facilities

Resources / facilities	Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Each senior staff has a comfortable furnished office	40.7% (11)	-	18.5% (5)	40.7% (11)
There are adequate books in the ratio of one student to ten volumes of books to cover all the area of the subject	18.5% (5)	-	22.2% (6)	59.3% (16)
There are adequate availability of current journals in agricultural education and other related fields in the ratio of one student to volumes of journals	22.2% (6)	-	25.9% (7)	51.9% (14)
Availability of a functional tractor with the necessary coupling implement e.g. plough, harrow, ridger etc	29.6% (8)	-	-	70.4% (19)
Availability of a functional haulage vehicle for transportation	7.4% (2)	-	11.1% (3)	81.5% (22)

Source: Field survey, 2025; *Values in parenthesis () are frequency values

Table 3. Frequency distribution of responses on the availability and adequacy of a functional Crops and livestock farms

Resources / facilities	Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
There is an existing arable farm containing tubers, cereals, legumes, and fibre crops on at least one hectare of land	11.1% (3)	-	51.9% (14)	37% (10)
There is horticultural garden containing nursery, ornamentals, fruits, root and leafy vegetable crops	-	-	51.9% (14)	48.1% (13)
There is an existing orchard containing assorted fruits trees	11.1% (3)	-	51.9% (14)	37% (10)
There is an existing permanent crops plantation	37% (10)	7.4% (2)	55.6% (15)	-
There are functional processing facilities for tubers, grains, fruits and vegetables	-	-	48.1% (13)	51.9% (14)
There are storage facilities for tubers, cereals, grains, fruits etc	-	-	37% (10)	63% (17)
There is an existing functional poultry housing system of a carrying capacity of 500 birds	11.1% (3)	-	55.6% (15)	33.3% (9)
There is a functional ruminant production unit of 20 animals capacity	-	-	55.6% (15)	44.4% (12)

Source: Field survey, 2025; *Values in parenthesis () are frequency values

Table 2 indicated that the respondents expressed disagreement with all the items: Each senior staff has a comfortable furnished office; there are adequate books in the ratio of one student to ten volumes of books to cover all the area of the subject; there are adequate availability of current journals in agricultural education and other related fields in the ratio of one student to volume of journals; availability of a functional tractor with the necessary coupling implement e.g. plough, harrow, ridger etc and availability of a functional haulage vehicle for transportation; with the sum percent and frequency values of 59.2% (16), 81.5% (22), 77.8% (21), 70.4% (19), and 92.6% (25), respectively, based on a four point scale estimation. The results suggest that the senior staff offices are neither adequately nor comfortably furnished; furthermore, there is insufficient availability of books, current journals, a functional tractor with necessary coupling implements, and a functional haulage vehicle for transportation in the study area.

While Table 3 depicted that the respondents disagreed in response with the items: There is an existing arable farm containing tubers, cereals, legumes, and fibre crops on at least one hectare of land; there is horticultural garden containing nursery, ornamentals, fruits, root and leafy vegetable crops; there is an existing orchard containing assorted fruits trees; there is an existing permanent crops plantation; there are functional processing facilities for tubers, grains, fruits and vegetables; there are storage facilities for tubers, cereals, grains, fruits etc; there is an existing functional poultry housing system of a carrying capacity of 500 birds; and there is a functional ruminant production unit of 20 animals capacity; with the total percentage and frequency values of 88.9% (24), 100% (27), 88.9% (24), 55.6% (15), 100% (27), 100% (27), 88.9% (24), and 100% (27), respectively, on a four point size appraisal. The findings of the present study as indicated in (Table 2 & 3) are in corroboration with the results of (Egbule, 2002; Egbita, 2007; & Kyarize, 2015) as earlier on expressed.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 1 and fig. 2 demonstrate a significant decrease in the number of admissions to the two Colleges of Education (College of Education, Warri and College of Education, Mosogar) examined over the 12-year admission period. The admission figures from the 2013/2014 to the 2024/2025 academic session have plummeted from 60 to 3 students and from 18 students to no admissions at all, respectively, in the State-owned Colleges of Education, Delta State. The findings of the study are in agreement with that of Freddie (2004) who averred that the decline in the number of students pursuing agriculture has been increasing over the years.

Table 4. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) on admission levels and the Delta State owned Colleges of Education

Colleges: COE Warri & COE Mosogar	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	450.667	1	450.667	2.847	.106
Within Groups	3482.667	22	158.303		
Total	3933.333	23			

*not significant at (P>0.05)

Table 4 Showed that there is no statistically significant difference (P>0.05) in the admission levels among the State-owned Colleges of Education investigated. This indicates that both Colleges of Education are similarly experiencing a notably low level of enrollment in the NCE agricultural education programmes, as mentioned earlier on.

Table 5. Showing the mean and standard error of means of the contemporary trends in NCE agricultural education programme in the State-owned Colleges of Education

Contemporary issues	N	Mean	Std. error of mean	Remarks
Inadequate funding of the NCE Agric. Edu. Programme	27	1.89	0.19	Accepted
Poor level of enrollment of students into NCE Agric. Edu. Programme	27	1.96	0.10	Accepted
Unfavourable environment for the NCE Agric. Edu. Programme	27	2.37	0.20	Accepted
Inadequate personnel in the NCE Agric. Edu. Programme	27	2.52	0.25	Not Accepted
Poor provision of infrastructural facilities	27	1.74	0.11	Accepted
Insufficient or non-availability of equipments	27	2.07	0.22	Accepted
Shortage of professional and technically qualified staff	27	2.26	0.24	Accepted
Declining quality of research and teaching	27	2.11	0.23	Accepted
Obsolete and unproductive curriculum	27	2.40	0.15	Accepted
Poor remuneration for both academic and non-academic staff	27	2.44	0.18	Accepted
Poor Education policy that are not in favour of Colleges of Education programmes	27	1.85	0.17	Accepted
Poor perception about College of Education Programmes	27	1.63	0.09	Accepted
The general admission requirements for students seeking admission into NCE Agric. Edu. programme	27	2.11	0.21	Accepted

Table 5 demonstrated that the inadequate funding of the NCE agricultural education programme, low level of enrollment, unfavourable environment, poor provision of infrastructural facilities, insufficient or non-availability of equipments, shortage of professional and technically qualified staff, declining quality of research and teaching, obsolete and unproductive curriculum, poor remuneration for both academic and non-academic staff, poor education policy that are not in favour of Colleges of Education programmes, poor perception about College of Education Programmes, the general admission requirements for students seeking admission into NCE agricultural education programme; with mean and standard error of mean estimations of 1.89 ± 0.19 , 1.96 ± 0.10 , 2.37 ± 0.20 , $1.74 \pm$

0.11, 2.07 ± 0.22 , 2.26 ± 0.24 , 2.11 ± 0.23 , 2.40 ± 0.15 , 2.44 ± 0.18 , 1.85 ± 0.17 , 1.63 ± 0.09 , and 2.11 ± 0.21 , respectively, represent the contemporary challenges facing the NCE agricultural education programme in the study area; with exception of the issue of inadequate personnel in the NCE Agricultural Education Programme with 2.52 ± 0.25 on a four point scale of evaluation. These results are in agreement with the findings of (Minna-Eyovwunu et al., 2020; Aina, 2009; Ekong & Eicher, 2006; Egbule, 2002; Egbita, 2007; Canice et al., 2007; Oyesola, 2016; Emmanuel, 2008; & Odetunde, 2004) as previously stated..

Table 6. Showing the summary of the non-parametric independent Sample T-test on contemporary issues affecting the NCE agricultural education programme in Delta State- owned Colleges of Education

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.^a	Decision
1	The distribution of inadequate funding of the NCE Agric. Edu. Programme is the same across the two State owned Colleges of Education	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.239	Retain the null hypothesis.
2	The distribution of Poor level of enrollment of students into NCE Agric. Edu. Programme is the same across the Colleges.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.906	Retain the null hypothesis.
3	The distribution of Unfavourable environment for the NCE Agric. Edu. Programme is the same across the Colleges.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.220	Retain the null hypothesis.
4	The distribution of Inadequate personnel in the NCE Agric. Edu. Programme is the same across categories of Colleges.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.405	Retain the null hypothesis.
5	The distribution of Poor provision of infrastructural facilities is the same across categories of Colleges.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.772	Retain the null hypothesis.
6	The distribution of Insufficient or non-availability of equipments is the same across categories of Colleges.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.270	Retain the null hypothesis.
7	The distribution of Shortage of professional and technically qualified staff is the same across categories of Colleges.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.365	Retain the null hypothesis.
8	The distribution of Declining quality of research and teaching is the same across categories of Colleges.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.268	Retain the null hypothesis.
9	The distribution of Obsolete and unproductive curriculum is the same across categories of Colleges.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.658	Retain the null hypothesis.
10	The distribution of Poor remuneration for both academic and non-academic staff is the same across categories of Colleges.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.179	Retain the null hypothesis.
11	The distribution of Poor education policy that are not in favour of Colleges of Education programmes is the same across categories of Colleges.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.259	Retain the null hypothesis.
12	The distribution of Poor perception about College of Education Programmes is the same across categories of Colleges.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.222	Retain the null hypothesis.
13	The distribution of the effect of the general admission requirements for students seeking admission into NCE Agric. Edu. programme is the same across categories of Colleges.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.184	Retain the null hypothesis.

Source: Field survey, 2025; ^a Not significant (P>0.05)

Table 6 indicates that there is no significant difference (P>0.05) between the State-owned Colleges of Education programmes examined regarding the highlighted contemporary issues impacting the NCE agricultural education programme assessed. This suggests that the contemporary trends influencing

the NCE agricultural education programme are consistent across the two Colleges of Education operated by the Delta State government.

CONCLUSION

The NCE agricultural education programme in State-owned Colleges of Education is currently facing numerous contemporary challenges: insufficient funding, low student enrollment rates, an unfavorable environment, inadequate infrastructural facilities, a lack of necessary equipment, a shortage of professionally and technically qualified personnel, a decline in the quality of research and teaching, an outdated and ineffective curriculum, inadequate compensation for both academic and non-academic staff, and educational policies that do not support the programmes of Colleges of Education, among others. There is a noticeable and significant decline in the admission rates to the Colleges of Education, which may be attributed to the various contemporary issues affecting the NCE agricultural education programme. Consequently, it is imperative to promote student enrollment in agricultural education programmes by establishing a supportive and efficient environment conducive to quality teaching and learning. An effective agricultural education programme environment should be staffed with technically and pedagogically qualified individuals and equipped with modern facilities and equipment as recommended for optimal teaching and learning.

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